

Excisional Hemorrhoidectomy Versus Minimal Invasive Processure for Hemorrhoids (Miph or Stapler Hemorrhoidopexy): A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Hemorrhoids are one of the most common anorectal disorders which affects almost 25-30% population. Hemorrhoids are very common in day to day practice. Many surgical and non-surgical treatment modalities are available for management of hemorrhoids. Out of which hemorrhoidectomy is regarded as the cure of disease. It can be performed in many ways. So it is necessary to find out the convenient treatment which is minimally invasive and less painful. Coventional open method is widely accepted by many surgeons. MIPH is a recent advance in the management of hemorrhoids.

Objective: To compare the efficacy and safety of the two most popular conventional method of treatment of hemorrhoids: Stapler hemorrhoidectomy and Excisional hemorrhoidectomy.

Material and Method: Study will be done on 50 patients of 3rd and 4th degree hemorrhoids having symptoms of bleeding per rectum or prolapsed; Coming to Nootan General Hospital will be randomly classified in to two

Groups: First group managed by stapler hemorrhoidectomy and second group managed by Excisional hemorrhoidectomy (25 patients in each group) after taking informed consent.(Group of patients will be randomly classified by computer generated random method). Study aimed at comparing the

duration of surgery, post-operative pain, analgesia requirement, duration of hospital stay, post-operative complications and the amount of days taken for return to work.

Result: Mean duration of surgery was 27.5 minutes in MIPH group and 51.5 minutes in open hemorrhoidectomy group. Compare to open hemorrhoidectomy group patients undergoing MIPH had lesser VAS pain score on postoperative days and require lesser analgesics. No patients in the MIPH group had residual prolapse. Time require to return to work was 5.5 days in MIPH group and 23.9 days in open hemorrhoidectomy group.

Conclusion: MIPH is effective in terms of decreased per- and postoperative blood loss, minimal pain, less requirement of analgesics and less pain at first bowel movement, faster wound healing with faster postoperative recovery and short postoperative hospital stay with early return to normal routine activity but MIPH is expensive as compared to open technique. However, long-term follow-ups necessary to determine whether these initial results are lasting.

Key words: MIPH (Stapler hemorrhoidectomy) ,Excisional hemorrhoidectomy.

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Introduction

Hemorrhoids are one of the most common anorectal disorders which affects almost 25-30% population. Hemorrhoids are very common in day to day practice. It is interchangeably known as Piles, but etymologically the words have different meanings.

The term 'haemorrhoid' is derived from the Greek adjective hemorrhoids meaning bleeding (haima=blood, rhoos=flowing). . On the other hand the term 'pile' is derived from the Latin word pila, meaning a Ball, which aptly can be used for all forms of hemorrhoids. It commonly Presents as mass protruding per rectum and fresh bleeding per rectum. They may be primarily due to heredity, natural consequences of adaptation of erect posture by mankind, straining to expel constipated stool or secondarily due to carcinoma of rectum, pregnancy, uterine tumour, and chronic constipation, dysuria due to stricture or enlarged prostate and portal Hypertension.

Hemorrhoids can be classified in many ways. Primarily they are divided into internal, external, and mixed types. Internal hemorrhoids are situated above the dentate line, covered with mucous membrane and external hemorrhoids lie below the dentate line, covered by skin. Another classification tells us the grading of the hemorrhoids ranging from grade I, being only symptomatic bleeding; grade II with spontaneous reduction of prolapsed hemorrhoids mass; grade III requiring manual repositioning of prolapsed hemorrhoids up to grade iv which are completely prolapsed hemorrhoids.

Grade I and early grade II hemorrhoids can be treated conservatively with laxative, dietary precautions, whereas grades III and IV require surgical interventions to treat the condition. Some grade II and III hemorrhoids can also be treated by Injection Sclerotherapy, banding or Infra-red/laser coagulation. The third type of classification determines hemorrhoids by their anatomical position, where 3, 7 and 11

o'clock are considered to be primary and the areas between to be Secondary.

There are various surgical methods available such as Ferguson's closed hemorrhoidectomy, Open Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy and Longo's Stapled Hemorrhoidopexy or MIPH. Open hemorrhoidectomy has long been regarded by the patients as an inherently painful procedure. Reduction of pain after hemorrhoidectomy is an important goal, with the ultimate aim of reduction in the length of hospital stay and the possibility of day care surgery. Hemorrhoidectomy by conventional technique causes considerable post-operative pain.

MIPH (Minimal Invasive Procedure for Hemorrhoids) is a new concept which is used to overcome these problems. Stapled hemorrhoidopexy for prolapsing hemorrhoids is conceptually different from Excisional hemorrhoidectomy. It does not accompany the pain that usually occurs after resection of the sensitive anoderm. Both procedures are effective in treating grade 3 and 4 hemorrhoids, however they both present with pros and cons as to which is the better Procedure under which circumstance.

Aims and Objective

To compare the duration of surgery, post-operative pain and analgesia, duration of hospital stay, post-operative complications and the amount of days taken for return to Work amongst patients undergoing MIPH and Open Hemorrhoidectomy.

Materials and methods

Study Design: Prospective comparative study

Settings: Department of surgery, Nootan general hospital, Visnagar, dist. mahesans, Gujarat

Study duration: 1st July 2022 to 31st December 2022.

Sample size: 50.out of 50 patients 25 patient underwent Longo technique of

MIPH and 25 patients underwent Milligan Morgan technique of open hemorrhoidectomy.

Inclusion criteria:

- Age: Between 20 to 70 years of age
- Sex: Both sex
- Patients of 3rd and 4th degree hemorrhoids.

Exclusion criteria: Patients with concomitant anal diseases like fissure in ano, Abscess, Perianal fistula and anorectal malignancy. Those patients who are not willing to give consent.

Study was approved by institutional ethical committee and is in line with the declaration of Helsinki and followed the guidelines laid out by Indian council of medical research. Written informed consent was taken from patients. Patient's hospital stay for analysis was calculated starting from the day of surgery. Pre-operatively patients were kept nil by mouth overnight and received a phosphate enema in the previous night of surgery. One dose of ceftriaxone 1gm and Metronidazole were given at the time of anesthesia for surgery.

All operations were performed in the lithotomy position under spinal anesthesia.

Pain was assessed using VAS Score. Follow-up was done at 1st, 2nd and 3rd weeks and between 4-6 weeks postoperatively. Operative times measure in minutes in the both the types of surgery. Immediate and short term post-operative pain assessed for first week. Postoperative bleeding measured as no, mild or profuse. Control of other symptoms like prolapse, pain, pruritus, anal incontinence to flatus and stool, anal stenosis will be assessed with patient's happiness.

Data of operative time, short term and long term postoperative pain, postoperative complication, postoperative symptoms free life with happiness will be collected and analyzed.

Results: A study has been undertaken to compare the results of two different surgical procedures for the treatment of 3rd degree & 4th degree Hemorrhoids i.e. open hemorrhoidectomy and MIPH (Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy). 50 cases of each were taken for this study with Careful follow up of these patients. In the present study, more patients belong to 41-50 years group, with mean age of patients was 46.3 years in miph group and 47.1 years in open hemorrhoidectomy group. (Table-1)

Table 1: Comparison of Age Distribution of Patients Studied

Age in years	MIPH		Open Hemorrhoidectomy		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
21-30	2	8%	2	8%	4	8%
31-40	6	24%	4	16%	10	20%
41-50	8	32%	9	36%	17	34%
51-60	6	24%	8	32%	14	28%
61-70	3	12%	2	8%	5	10%
Total	25	100%	25	100%	50	100%

Majority of patients were Male in our study (80% male in MIPH group and 72% male in open hemorrhoidectomy group) (Table-2)

Table 2: Comparison of Gender Distribution of Patients Studied

Gender	MIPH		Open hemorrhoidectomy		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Male	20	80%	18	72%	38	76%
Female	5	20%	7	28%	12	24%
Total	25	100%	25	100%	50	100%

On comparing socioeconomic status, majority of patients in MIPH group belongs to upper (60%) and middle (36%) socioeconomic class, whereas in open hemorrhoidectomy group majority of patients belongs to lower (76%) socioeconomic class. (Table-3)

Table 3: Comparison of Socioeconomic Status of Patients Studied

Socio economic status	MIPH		Open hemorrhoidectomy		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Lower	1	4%	19	76%	20	40%
Middle	9	36%	6	24%	15	30%
Upper	15	60%	0	0%	15	30%
Total	25	100%	25	100%	50	100%

All patients in both groups are presented with symptoms of bleeding per anum and prolapsed mass, while 20 patients in MIPH group and 21 patients in open hemorrhoidectomy group are presented with symptoms of pain. Only 12 patients in MIPH group and 10 patients in open hemorrhoidectomy group are presented with pruritus.(Table-5)

Table 5: Comparison of Clinical Presentation in Two Groups

Clinical presentation	MIPH		Open hemorrhoidectomy		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Bleeding	25	100%	25	100%	50	100%
Prolapse mass	25	100%	25	100%	50	100%
Pain	20	80%	21	84%	41	82%
Pruritus	12	48%	10	40%	22	44%

Mean duration of surgery was 27.5 minutes in MIPH group and 51.5 minutes in open hemorrhoidectomy group. Thus average duration of surgery in open hemorrhoidectomy was 50 minutes as compare to 30 minutes in MIPH group. These data clearly shows that duration of surgery was quite less in MIPH group. Most of the patients (68%) in MIPH group complained of mild post-operative pain which subside by only giving analgesic. While most of the patents (52%) in open

hemorrhoidectomy group complained of moderate amount of postoperative pain which require round the clock analgesics. Only 12% patients in MIPH group complained of severe postoperative pain compare to open hemorrhoidectomy group in which 28% patients complained of severe postoperative pain which require strong opioid analgesics and sedatives. Analgesia requirement was significantly lower in MIPH group. (Table-6)

Table 6: Comparison of Postoperative Pain Score in Both Groups

Postoperative pain score	MIPH		Open Hemorrhoidectomy	
	No	%	No	%
Mild (0-3)	17	68%	5	20%
Moderate (4-7)	5	20%	13	52%
Severe (8-10)	3	12%	7	28%

Only 4% patients in MIPH group complained of immediate post op bleeding compare to 20% patients in open hemorrhoidectomy group complained of immediate post op bleeding which was in

form of soakage of dressing or few drops blood while passing faeces.

28% patients in open hemorrhoidectomy group developed post op urinary retention out of which 11% patients require

catheterization and rest of patients require analgesics and hot water fomentation for relief. In comparison to MIPH group only 4% patients developed post op urinary retention which requires only hot fomentation and analgesic.

20% patients in open hemorrhoidectomy group complained of short term post op incontinence to flatus as compared to 0% patients in MIPH group complained of incontinence to flatus.(Table-7)

Table 7: Comparison of Immediate Post of Complications

Post op complications	MIPH		Open hemorrhoidectomy		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Bleeding	1	0%	5	20%	6	12%
Retention of urine	1	4%	7	28%	8	16%
Incontinence to flatus	0	0%	5	20%	5	10%

Mean duration of time needed to return to work was 5.5 days in MIPH group (100%) compare to 23.9 days in open hemorrhoidectomy group which was much earlier than open group. Though MIPH is costly, early resumption to work helps economically to the patients.(Table-8)

Table 8: Comparison of Require Total Time to Resume Routine Work

Days	MIPH		Open Hemorrhoidectomy	
	No	%	No	%
1-10 days	25	100%	0	0%
11-20 days	0	0%	4	16%
21-30 days	0	0%	21	84%
Total	25	100%	25	100%

Discussion

For symptomatic grade 3 and 4 hemorrhoids, some form of hemorrhoidectomy remains the accepted modality of treatment. The traditional methods like the Milligan—Morgan method [1] and the Ferguson’s method [2] have been in practice for more than half a century for want of a better alternative. Recent years have seen the introduction of newer techniques with relative merits and demerits. The most significant recent introduction has been the circular stapling device (MIPH) for prolapsed haemorrhoids. This has been criticized for not treating the external component of haemorrhoids and the skin tags. Additionally the stapler cartridges are expensive and beyond the reach of most patients.

In present study both groups were demographically comparable. Mean age in our study was 46.3 years. Thirumalagiri et al conducted similar study in which mean age

of presentation 45.8 years. Male patients were more in number in both groups of patients. In our study, the most commonly affected people in MIPH group belonged to upper (60%) and middle class (36%), while in open hemorrhoidectomy group, maximum number of patients (40%) came from lower class. This was most likely due to cost effectiveness of open hemorrhoidectomy as compared to MIPH owing to additional cost of stapler in later group.

In the present study, only patients with grade 3 and grade 4 hemorrhoids were included with presenting complaints of bleeding and prolapsed mass. Few patients presented with complaints of pain and pruritus. In the study done by Thirumalagiri et al, bleeding, pain And mass per rectum were the most common complaints in patients of grade III and grade IV.[7]Rathore et al, in their study included patients with second and third degree of hemorrhoids, who mostly visited hospital

with the complaints of bleeding per rectum and prolapsed of piles during defecation.

In the study done by Iqbal et al, of total fifty Eight patients who underwent stapled hemorrhoidectomy, 3(5.17%) had second degree, 46(79.31%) had third degree hemorrhoids and 9(15.51%) had fourth degree hemorrhoids respectively. The most common problem reported pre operatively was something coming out Of the anus. Others included bleeding, itching, discharge and pain.

Mean duration of surgery was 27.5 minutes and 51.5 minutes in MIPH and Open hemorrhoidectomy group respectively. Statistically significant difference was seen in the duration of surgery amongst the two groups .In the study done by Thirumalagiri et al, the operating time for stapler hemorrhoidectomy was 28.7 minutes and for open hemorrhoidectomy was 36.2 minutes. The mean operating time for open group was significantly higher than the stapled group in the study conducted by Baliga et al. Pain in MIPH group was significantly lesser as compared to open hemorrhoidectomy group as hemorrhoidopexy is performed above the dentate line, where mucosa is insensitive to pain. Similar findings were observed in studies done by Baliga et al and Kim et al.

The requirement of analgesia in MIPH group was significantly lesser compare to open group. Total complications were significantly higher in patients who underwent open hemorrhoidectomy in our study. Baliga et al, the stapled hemorrhoidectomy group had an incidence of complications of 20% compared to 30% for the open hemorrhoidectomy group, the difference was not statistically significant. In another study, the postoperative bleeding rate was 4.9 % in both groups and the rate of urinary retention did not differ significantly (4.9 % vs. 1.6 %).The mean duration of stay at hospital was significantly lower in the MIPH group .Lesser duration of stay was due to faster

recovery in MIPH group. In the study done by Thirumalagiri et al, mean post-operative hospital stay in MIPH group was 1.1 ± 0.35 days and 2.3 ± 1.2 days in open hemorrhoidectomy group, which was statistically significant. In study by Gravie et al, Hospital stay was significantly shorter in the stapled hemorrhoidectomy group $2.2 \text{ days} \pm 1.2$ as compared to open hemorrhoidectomy group $3.1 \text{ days} \pm 1.7$.

Mean duration of time needed to return to work in MIPH group was significantly lesser as compared to Open hemorrhoidectomy. In study done by Aggarwal et al, in the open hemorrhoidectomy group, the patients returned to work postoperatively in twenty five days on average (range: 20-30 days), in the stapler-hemorrhoidopexy group, 52% were able to return to their normal routine and work in two days , 32% in three days and only 16% in four days.

MIPH is expensive as compared to open technique. In open group there were many factors to increase expenses like longer postoperative hospital stay and late resumption of routine work(resulting in loss of working days), but MIPH is still more costlier. Disposable nature of MIPH instrument increases cost of therapy but future advances in MIPH can make it cheaper, re-usable and universally available.

Conclusion

Conventional hemorrhoidectomy is still performed in many higher centers but in this era of minimal invasive surgery, stapler hemorrhoidopexy is fast replacing conventional hemorrhoidectomy. Following conclusions have been summarized from the study:

- Out of the two techniques, open hemorrhoidectomy is universally available, simple to learn, economical procedure with few complications and associated with longer wound care and long duration of morbidity.

- MIPH has less peri-operative and post-operative complications. Patients undergone MIPH had less blood loss with less postoperative pain and morbidity.
- MIPH is associated with shorter postoperative hospital stay and quicker return to routine work. MIPH has greater patient satisfaction and better functional outcome – quality of life.
- Though MIPH is costly, early resumption of work may help economically.
- MIPH has a longer learning period but duration of surgery can be shortened with experience.
- Disposable nature of MIPH instrument increases cost of therapy but future advances in MIPH can make it cheaper, re-usable and universally available.

Both surgical modalities are equally efficacious in curing internal hemorrhoids but open hemorrhoidectomy is preferred for internal hemorrhoids with anal fissure, anal fistula, skin tags and external hemorrhoids.

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